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Information Technology Teachers and Students Acceptability of Open Education Resources (OERs) Using the Diffusion of Innovation Theory: Towards the Adoption of a Flipped Classroom

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to determine the acceptability of IT teachers and students in a Higher Education Institution on the use of Open Education Resources (OERs) for teaching and learning. It made use of Roger's Diffusion of Innovation theory attributes namely: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, triability and observability to determine its acceptability towards adoption. The researchers made use of two separate questionnaires, that is, one for the faculty and another for the students. The two questionnaires made use of a Likert scale with "4" as a number that represents strongly agree and "1" for strongly disagree. Responses from the IT and Computer Engineering faculty and IT students were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The one-way ANOVA was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the faculty members responses when grouped according to years of teaching experience. One-way ANOVA was also used to determine the significant difference of student's responses when grouped according to year level. The results revealed that there is no significant difference in the responses of the faculty when grouped according to years of teaching. Similarly, the results showed that there is no significant difference in the students' responses when grouped according to year level. The results of the study was used as bases for the development of the OER-based flipped classroom syllabus which will serve as the model for the IT and Computer Engineering faculty OER training which is the first step towards adoption and utilization.

Keywords: Open education, innovative teaching approach, free educational resources

INTRODUCTION

The adoption of OER provides an opportunity to use and share quality free educational resources, but there are challenges, such as awareness and engagement that needs to be addressed. However, despite various efforts to promote the use of OERs in educational institutions, it is not adopted which impacts sustainability and realization of its purpose (USAID, 2020). In the study of Villanueva, S. and Dolom, MA (2018), the adoption of OER relies on the attitude and perceived usefulness. These are measures of acceptability which means that the more users perceive OER's usefulness the bigger chance of acceptability. This is the reason, the researchers conducted research to determine the acceptability of OER using Roger's Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory to introduce OER in the School of Engineering Architecture and Information Technology's IT department which

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at present is a Center of Development mandated to introduce and pioneer innovations using technology.

Roger's Diffusion of Innovation uses five attributes namely: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, triability and observability to determine the adoption of an innovation like OER (Menzli, et al., 2022; Buć and Divjak (2015), Jwaifell and Gasaymeh, (2013). Relative advantage refers to the acceptability of the users in terms of the benefits that they can get from the innovation. The more they believe that the innovation is beneficial for them, the higher the rate of adoption. Compatibility on the other hand is the perception that the innovation can address the values and needs of the users. Complexity refers to the ease of use of the innovation. Triability is the degree to which the innovation can be experimented on and observability refers to the degree where the results can be observed by the users.

OERs can contribute to the improvement of flipped classroom because it is used to augment learning of students by providing them with resources from OERs to boost students' learning and improve comprehension and reading, collaborative work, and critical-thinking and creativity (Mosquera Feijoo, et al., 2021; Li, Y., Zhang, M., Bonk, C.J., Zhang, W., Guo, Y., 2017). The same is true with the teachers where OERs provide free ready to use educational resources (Badai, Ajmi and Naidu, 2017).

With the benefits of using OER in mind, the researchers conducted a study on the acceptability of IT and Computer Engineering teachers and IT students on OERs in the SEAIT IT Department. The findings of the study were used as a guide or basis for a project that will realize the adoption of OER. That is, an OER-based flipped classroom syllabus was developed and trainings for teachers and IT students was conducted.

METHODOLOGY

This study is applied research whereby researchers determined the acceptability of OER of Information Technology (IT) teachers and students using Roger's Diffusion of Innovation Theory. The results of the acceptability survey were used to design and develop an IT course OER-Based flipped classroom syllabus, IT Teachers' OER Training and an orientation for IT students, if found that it is needed. A questionnaire with the DOI five (5) attributes namely, relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, triability and observability was used to determine the acceptability of IT teachers and students. The researchers adopted the OER DOI 5-point Likert scale questionnaire used by Menzli et al. (2022) for teachers. For the students, the researchers adopted the DOI questionnaire of Afolabi, F. (2017). The computed reliability coefficient for both questionnaires is 0.85. The mean and standard deviation was used to describe the data gathered from the OER DOI questionnaire. One-way ANOVA was used to determine the difference in the OER acceptability of IT teachers when grouped according to years of teaching experience. The results of the survey were used to design and develop the IT teachers' OER training. ANOVA test was also used to determine the difference in the OER acceptability of students when grouped according to year level. The results of the study will serve as a basis in designing the IT course OER-based flipped

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classroom syllabus, IT and Engineering teachers OER training and OER orientation of students.

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University (SMU), School of Engineering, Architecture and Information Technology (SEAIT), IT department of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The IT Department was awarded Center of Development (COD) in IT Education since 2007. As a COD, the IT Department's mandate is to continuously develop and improve HEIs by enhancing their teaching, research, and service programs. The use of OER for teaching and learning is one opportunity that would be a tool to realize its mandate.

The respondents of this study supposedly all or four (4) IT teachers except for the proponents of this study and one hundred forty-nine (149) IT students of the SEAIT, IT department of the current semester of S.Y. 2022-2023. However, three (3) IT teachers did not answer the questionnaire, hence the researchers invited two (2) Computer Engineering teachers who answered the questionnaire. The IT students come from the different levels, that is, from 1st year to 4th year enrolled in the second semester of this school year.

The DOI questionnaire that was used to determine the teachers and students OER acceptability was adopted from the study of Menzli, et al. (2022). The DOI questionnaire has 28 items with a five-point Likert Scale where "5" strongly agree to "1" being strongly disagree. The relative value is composed of seven (7) questions, compatibility six (6), four (4) for complexity, six (6) for triability, and six (6) for observability. The respondents of the DOI questionnaire may choose to answer in print or through a google form link that was distributed to both students and teachers. The questionnaire used for the students was adopted from the study of Afolabi, F. (2017).

A letter was written to the OIC Dean of the School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology to allow the researchers to distribute the printed questionnaire or provide the link of the DOI questionnaire to all IT teachers with teaching loads and students enrolled in the current semester. The questionnaire was in print and in an electronic or google form link. The researchers visited classes of IT students and teachers in their classes and shared links of the OER questionnaire and consent forms. Although there are only few cases of COVID 19 in the university, the proponents observed the minimum health protocol, that is, observing physical distancing and wearing face mask during the distribution of questionnaires, consent forms and google form link for those opted to answer online. Before the distribution, the researchers informed respondents that answering the questionnaire is not required, but voluntary and that it will not affect their academic performance in any way. The respondents were also informed that if they decide to answer the questionnaire, all their answers will be treated with confidentiality and that only the researchers will be able to see their answers. Also, the researchers informed that all accomplished questionnaires were shredded and that online answers via google form will be erased once the research is already through and presented in a fora. The researchers through their consent forms explained the importance of giving honest, truthful, and biased-free answers for the successful results of the research. The answers in google form were extracted in Excel format. Since all respondents opted to answer online the downloaded answers from the google form was deleted immediately after the presentation in a research fora. The extracted answers were imported to MS Excel or SPSS for analysis.

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The mean and standard deviation was used to determine OER acceptability of the respondents in terms of (1) relative advantage, (2) compatibility, (3) complexity, (4) trialability, and (5) observability. It was also used to compare the responses of the IT teachers with the students and determine the attribute or attributes that affect or affects adoption of OER. The one-way ANOVA was used to determine if there is a difference in the OER acceptability of the IT teachers in terms of years of teaching experience. Similarly, ANOVA was also used to determine if there is a difference in the OER acceptability of IT students based on their year level. The results will be utilized by serving as basis for the design of the OER training for IT teachers and OER-based IT course flipped classroom. All answers were treated with utmost confidentiality. Google form was used for the questionnaires and the name of the respondents was optional. The email address of the respondents was not recorded to keep confidentiality.

This study was submitted to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) for ethics review. The two (2) collaborators who are also IT teachers was excluded from answering the DOI questionnaire to prevent bias in the responses. The proponents recognized the fact that there is a perceived conflict of interest because the researchers are colleagues to the IT teacher-respondents or that they are from the same department hence there is a friendly relationship that might influence the responses and affect the results of the survey. Having known this, the researchers, to address concerns on vulnerability, the proponents included a clause that will make the respondents promise that their answers are true, honest, and objective and not influenced by the proponents. The proponents also emphasized that answering the DOI questionnaire is voluntary. It means not answering the questionnaire is their own choice and it was respected by the researchers. For the perceived influence of the researchers on the IT students, the researchers also emphasized to the students that answering the questionnaire is voluntary and that it will not affect the students' academic performance in whatever way. The importance of answering the questionnaire truthfully and getting biased-free answers from the IT teachers and IT students was emphasized. Respondents were requested to answer the questionnaire either in print or in google form voluntarily and were not forced to answer if they do not want to. Health protocols such as physical distancing and wearing of face mask was observed during the face-to-face distribution of questionnaire and training of teachers. No financial remuneration was released to respondents in exchange of answering the questionnaire. Even if they have chosen to participate voluntarily, they will have the right to refuse to continue and any information they have already provided will not be used in the study.

RESULTS

Respondents Profile

Out of four (4) identified teacher respondents, only one (1) accomplished the questionnaire. On the otherhand, out of the two (2) Computer Engineering fulltime teachers, both or 100% answer ed the questionnaire. Out of the three (3) respondents, two (2) or

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67% are Assistant Instructors and one (1) or 33% is an Associate Professor. Moreover, all the respondents are female teachers.

Out of one hundred forty-nine (149) BSIT students enrolled in the semester, there were seventy-five (75) or 50% answered the questionnaire. Twenty-one (21) are first (1st) year students, eighteen (18) are second (2nd) year, twenty-two (22) are third (3rd) year and fourteen (14) are fourth (4th) year students. In terms of sex, fifty-three (53) are male and twenty-two (22) are female BSIT students.

OER Acceptability of IT and Computer Engineering Teachers and IT Students

Table 1 and 2 displays the results of the acceptability of IT and Computer Engineering teachers and IT students using DOI, respectively.

Table 1. OER acceptability of IT and Computer Engineering Teachers

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Relative Advantage			
1. You can save money by using OER	3.33	0.57	Agree
2. You can save effort by using OER	3.33	0.57	Agree
3. You can save time by using OER	3.33	0.57	Agree
4. OER contribute to building students' capabilities	3.33	0.57	Agree
5. Sharing OER enhances my teacher reputation	3.33	0.57	Agree
6. Using OER can enhance the reputation of my university	3.67	0.57	Agree
7. OER help me to be more effective	3.67	0.57	Agree
Overall Mean:	3.42		
Compatibility			
1. I don't accept others to review my educational resources	2.33	0.57	Disagree
2. I don't want to share my resources with others because I spent so much time and effort preparing them	2.33	0.57	Disagree
3. I don't trust other people to mention my name when sharing my resources	2.33	0.57	Disagree
4. I'm afraid of misuse of my own OER	2.33	0.57	Disagree
5. When sharing my resources, I'm afraid of misuse of Creative Commons license	2.67	0.57	Disagree
Overall Mean:	2.4		
Complexity			
1. It is easy for me to use OER	3.33	0.57	Agree

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2. I find that dealing with OER is clear and understandable	3.66	0.57	Agree
3. Creative Commons licenses are difficult to find in educational resources	3	0	Agree
4. It is difficult for me to build Creative Commons licenses	2.66	0.57	Disagree
Overall Mean:	3.16		
Triability			
1. I want to try to use OER before effective adoption in teaching	3	0	Agree
2. I want to try to use OER before effective adoption in research	3	0	Agree
3. I want to try to use OER before effective adoption in training	3	0	Agree
4. My university allows staff to try using OER before effective adoption in teaching	3	0	Agree
5. My university allows staff to try using OER before effective adoption in research	3	0	Agree
6. My university allows staff to try using OER before effective adoption in training	3	0	Agree
Overall Mean:	3		
Observability			
1. OER provide opportunities to share research with others	3.33	0.57	Agree
2. OER provide opportunities for partnership in teaching	3.33	0.57	Agree
3. OER provide opportunities for sharing the teaching tasks	3.33	0.57	Agree
4. OER encourage cooperative learning	3.33	0.57	Agree
5. Creative Commons Licenses provide the possibility to benefit from the experiences of others	3	0	Agree
6. I don't see any benefit in mixing other people's work	2	0	Disagree
Overall Mean:	3.05		

The table above reveals that generally, the respondents have a positive attitude towards the adoption of OER, hence, it can be deduced that the respondents accept the adoption of OER in their department. Since acceptance and adoption models, like DOI are used to determine the success of a product's implementation. The higher the acceptance, the bigger chance of adoption and implementation.

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In terms of relative advantage, generally, respondents perceive that OER has advantages and opportunities when adopted. These advantages are saving money, effort, and time. Using OER is also perceived to enhance their reputation and the university. Aside from this, they also perceive that OER will help them be more effective. In terms of compatibility, the respondents are willing to share the educational resources that they have prepared. This might be due to the reason that sharing of resources builds the reputation of a teacher as an expert in his/her field. Sharing of resources also increases their professional value because through sharing will help other teachers to grow.

Table 2. OER Acceptability of IT Students

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Relative Advantage			
1. The OER is a positive innovation.	3.30	0.54	Agree
2. OER makes it more convenient to communicate with facilitators and friends.	3.30	0.51	Agree
3. Using OER saves time.	3.32	0.54	Agree
4. OER makes learning more meaningful.	3.24	0.53	Agree
5. OER is the fast and efficient way of getting information.	3.33	0.59	Agree
Overall Mean:	3.30		
Compatibility			
1. Using OER would require me to change my study habit.	2.96	0.74	Disagree
2. I am eager to respond to the discussion group on OER via LMS.	2.97	0.69	Disagree
3. OER is compatible with the way I study.	3.20	0.61	Agree
4. Using OER increases my interaction with the subject matter.	3.20	0.58	Agree
Overall Mean:	3.15		
Complexity			
1. OER is user friendly.	3.24	0.62	Agree
2. When using OER, I find it easy to navigate from one screen to another.	3.13	0.67	Agree
3. I am confident in my ability to use OER.	3.08	0.62	Agree
Overall Mean:	3.15		
Triability			
1. OER do not intimidate me.	3.04	0.70	Agree
2. I am confident in my ability to try OER.	3.05	0.69	Agree
3. I do trial and error in working with OER	3.16	0.56	Agree
4. I can learn at a comfortable pace using OER	3.09	0.57	Agree

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	Overall Mean:	3.08		
Observability				
1.	I am aware of OER even before I got admitted in SMU	2.58	0.76	Disagree
2.	OER makes teaching real	2.90	0.63	Disagree
3.	I have seen other schools using OER	2.69	0.81	Disagree
	Overall Mean:	2.72		

The table above shows that IT students perceive that OER has a relative advantage and that it is a positive innovation for learning. Similar with the teachers, they agree that OER saves time and effort for it is a tool to get information fast and easy. While the results showed that teachers believe that OER will help them to teach more effectively, the students on the otherhand believe that OER makes learning more meaningful. In terms of compatibility, the students agree that the use of OER is compatible with the way they study and that it will increase interaction with the subject matter. This might be attributed to the type of learning resources and activities that BSIT students are currently using, these are digitalized resources accessible via Learning Management System (LMS) that can be accessed through technological devices, such as laptops, mobile phones and tablets. Similarly, students find OER as user friendly and easy to navigate. Moreover, they are confident in their ability to use the OER maybe because of the above reason that respondents are BSIT students who are familiar with digitalized resources and technology. The above results also showed that since students are confident in their ability to use OER, they too are confident to try OER. The results from the above table revealed that most of the respondents are not aware of OER before they got admitted in SMU nor they have seen other schools use OER. Despite the perceived relative advantages of OER, respondents do not believe that OER makes teaching real. This maybe because OER are perceived only as supplementary resources and teachers still need to play a vital role to learn and awareness of its benefits still needs to be improved.

DOI attribute(s) that affects IT teachers and students OER adoption most

The DOI attribute that affects the teachers and students OER acceptability most is the relative advantage. Compared to the results of other DOI attributes, the average mean of the relative advantage for both teachers and IT students are the highest, these are 3.42 and 3.30, respectively. These results reveal that both teachers and IT students perceived that the OER was beneficial for teaching and learning. Since the respondents, both teachers and students perceived that OER has advantages, the adoption of OER is encouraged.

Difference in the OER acceptability of IT and Computer Engineering teachers when grouped according to years of teaching experience

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The table below shows the results using one-way ANOVA to determine if there is a significant difference in OER acceptability of teachers when grouped according to years of teaching service.

Table 3: Comparison of OER Acceptability response

One-way ANOVA

SUMMARY				
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
5 years	5	14.72	2.944	0.23163
22 years	5	15.68	3.136	0.16473

ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.09216	1	0.09216	0.46	0.51	5.32
Within Groups	1.58544	8	0.19818			
Total	1.6776	9				

The table above reveals that there is no statistically significant difference between the means of the faculty responses when grouped according to years of teaching experience, therefore we cannot conclude that years of teaching experience affects OER acceptability.

Difference in the OER acceptability of IT students when grouped according to years of teaching experience

Table 4: Comparison of IT Students OER Acceptability response

One-way ANOVA

SUMMARY				
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
1	5	15.13	3.026	0.01963
2	5	15.11	3.022	0.03937
3	5	16.2	3.24	0.05715
4	5	15.17	3.034	0.05108

ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.169975	3	0.056658	1.35	0.29	3.23
Within Groups	0.66892	16	0.041808			
Total	0.838895	19				

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The table above reveals that there is no significant difference in the OER acceptability of IT students when grouped according to year level. This explains that results of OER acceptability cannot be attributed to IT students' year level.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings of this study shows that the generally the faculty and IT students has a positive attitude towards OER. It shows that they are willing to adopt the OER for their teaching and learning.

In terms of relative advantage, both faculty and students perceive the OER as beneficial in terms of saving money, effort, time while building students' capabilities. They find OER as a positive innovation that will make learning more meaningful and is a fast and efficient way of getting information. This may be because they are aware that OERs are open, free, shareable and reused for a better teaching and learning similar with the findings of Tlili, A., et al. (2021) and Hylèn, J. (2021). Faculty can use and reuse educational resources developed by other faculty members legally, that is, for educational resource uploaded in the internet under Creative Commons licenses.

In terms of compatibility, the teachers are open to sharing the resources that they have developed and are alright with other expert to critique it for learning resources improvement. They are open to the concept of sharing of resources and recognize the benefits of sharing as an opportunity to collaborate and partner with other teachers. Aside from these, they also perceive that OER will provide them the opportunity to share teaching tasks in developing resources and that it results to cooperative learning helping each faculty to grow professionally as teachers. Sharing of resources is one of OERs is one of the advantages that OERs advocate, and that USAID (2020) emphasized the importance of sharing resources. The students on the otherhand, perceive that using OERs would not require them to change their study habit. This maybe because the respondents are IT students who are familiar with internet resources and use of e-learning tools such as Learning Management Systems which includes downloading and uploading resources from a tool that is powered by internet like OER. In the study of Buć, S. and Divjak, B. (2015), they wrote that OERs can be beneficial specially now a days that most instructions are delivered in an e-learning environment.

The faculty respondents and the IT students do not find OER as complex, this may be because the respondents are all familiar with the use of technology and the internet where OERs can be found. Both teachers and IT students are confident and are not intimidated on the adoption and utilization of OERs for teaching and learning. This may be a sure sign that the utilization and the integration of OERs as an integral part of teaching and learning inside the classroom whether it be for face-to-face or blended learning will be a success. However, this study revealed that despite their familiarity with the internet the teachers are not familiar with the Creative Commons licenses, that is in finding and building licenses. Government agencies like the Commission on Higher Education and Department of Education in partnership with USAID might be aware of this concern, hence they have

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conducted trainings on OERs and Creative Commons licenses (USAID, 2020). Having this finding in the study, the researchers see the need to focus on the Creative Commons Licenses in trainings or seminars that will be conducted in the future, that is, for the teachers to fully appreciate and implement the use of OERs.

Despite the positive response towards the adoption of OERs in this institution, the respondents, IT students particularly are not aware of OERs. This study revealed that OERs are not commonly used in other schools, either. The study of Javillonar, Pregrino and Caballes (2020), revealed that despite the positive response on the advantages of using OERs and the teachers' willingness to adopt OER, awareness remains an issue. They wrote that awareness is a key to a successful adoption and implementation of OER and that they recommend that the training on OER should be strengthened to make teachers fully aware and be ready for its successful implementation.

Using the one-way ANOVA, the findings of the study showed that there is no difference in the OER acceptability of teachers when grouped according to years of service. The same with the IT students that showed no difference in the OER acceptance when grouped according to year level. This finding might be attributed to the fact that OERs are not widely utilized, and many are not yet aware, if not OERs are not widely utilized in the Philippines, despite the efforts from CHED and DepEd to integrate OERs in classroom teaching (Javillonar, Pregrino and Caballes (2020); Arinto and Cantada, 2013). Since classes are now using the face-to-face mode of instruction delivery, the researchers propose to utilize OER to the fullest by integrating using the flipped classroom approach. In the study of Mosquera, F., et al. (2021), flipped classroom was used to augment learning of students by providing them with resources from OERs to boost students' learnings and improve comprehension and reading, collaborative work, critical-thinking and creativity. With this in mind, the researchers will develop an OER-based flipped classroom syllabus to serve as a model for teacher's training.

The researchers despite its efforts to gather responses from all identified respondents, cannot because it is emphasized that answering the questionnaire is voluntary. This could be the reason why the number of respondents, both from teachers and IT students is only limited to those who wanted and are willing to answer the questionnaire.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers conclude that an OER capacity building project or training is welcomed and accepted by both IT and Computer Engineering teachers and IT students. The researchers also conclude that both teachers and students perceive OERs as advantageous for teaching and learning, more so in saving time and cost of educational resources. The use of OERs is compatible with the existing way or method that teachers teach and students learn. Also, OERs' are not complex for them to use in their teaching and learning and that they will try and adopt OER as part of their classroom delivery provided that prior to adoption and implementation, they may be trained first for its effective integration. Of the five (5) DOI attributes, relative advantage is the attribute that contributed

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most to the reason that both teachers and students accepts the adoption of OER. The researchers also conclude that years of service of teachers and the students' year level do not affect the acceptance of OER for adoption. Despite the positive attitude of respondents towards the adoption of OER in their teaching and learning, based on the findings, it can be deduce that the teachers and IT students are not fully aware of OER which resulted to non-utilization of OER. With this, it is therefore concluded that an OER project which includes increasing awareness, use of OERs and its integration in the classroom setting is needed for a successful OER adoption.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researchers recommend that the adoption of an OER project in the IT Department be considered. The OER project can start with increasing of teachers' awareness for its utilization, followed by series of trainings on the integration of OERs in classroom teaching and learning. The development of an OER-based syllabus to serve as teachers' model in the integration of OERs in the classroom for an assured utilization is also recommended. An orientation for students on the use of OER be included in the training to increase students awareness and appreciation is also suggested.

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